

Complexes of Metal Ions with Phosphorus or Arsenic Containing Ligands. Part XIV. Complexes of Silver(I)Nitrate with Ethylene-1, 2-bisdiphenylphosphine/Arsine and Butylene-1, 4-bisdiphenylarsine

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Received 23 July 1971

Ditertiaryphosphines/arsines of the type' $(C_6H_5)_2E(CH_2)_nE(C_6H_5)_2$ (E is P or As) react with silver nitrate to yield complexes having the empirical formula, $LAgNO_3 \cdot xH_2O$. The ir spectra indicate the presence of bidentate nitrate groups. An ionic structure having octahedral environments around silver(I) has been proposed for these complexes. However, an equilibrium between covalent structure and ionic structure has been postulated for the complex where E is AS, n is 4 and x is 2.

Complexes of silver (I) with monotertiary phosphines/arsines have been reported in literature¹⁻⁴. Ditertiaryphosphines/arsines usually yield four coordinated silver (I) complexes^{5,6}. We have already reported the complexes of copper (I), silver (I) and gold (I) halides with ditertiary phosphines/arsines^{7,8}. In the present communication complexes of silver(I) nitrate with ligands; ethylene-1,2-bisdiphenylphosphine (EDP), ethylene-1,2-bisdiphenylarsine (EDA) and butylene-1,4-bisdiphenylarsine (BDA) are being reported.

RESULTS

Silver nitrate reacts with EDP, EDA and BDA in acetone to yield complexes, analytical results of which conform to the general formula, $LAgNO_3 \cdot xH_2O$ (where L is EDP or BDA; x is 2 and when L is EDA; x is 1). The infrared spectra of the ligands and the complexes have been recorded in nujol mull and KBr (Table 1). The presence of water molecules have been indicated in the infrared spectra. The number of ir bands, intensity sequence and position of bands in the region 1500, 1200, 1000 and 800 cm^{-1} indicate that nitrate groups are acting as bidentate^{9,10}. Bands at 1110, 1070 and 1068 cm^{-1} due to $P-C_{(Ar)}$ or $As-C_{(Ar)}$ bond stretches in the complexes EDP, EDA and BDA respectively have been recorded. Thus an increase of 7-12 cm^{-1} in $P-C_{(Ar)}$ and $As-C_{(Ar)}$ stretching frequency indicates coordination of donor atoms to the metal ion^{7,8,11}. The molar conductance measurements in nitrobenzene (Table 1) show that complexes of silver (I) nitrate with EDP and EDA are uni-univalent electrolytes and indicate the presence of ionic structures, $[(EDP)_2(H_2O)_2Ag][Ag(NO_3)_2(H_2O)_2]$ and $[(EDA)_2(H_2O)_2Ag][Ag(NO_3)_2]$. In these complexes cation is octahedral and anion may be octahedral or tetrahedral. The low conductance value for the complex

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TABLE I

Molar conductance and infrared spectral data

S.No.	Ligand/Complex	Molar conductance ohm ⁻¹ cm ² mol ⁻¹	P-C _(Ar) As-C _(Ar) stretch cm ⁻¹	Water	Nitrate
1.	EDP		1092, sp		
2.	EDA		1070m, sp		
3.	BDA		1068m, sp		
4.	(EDP)AgNO ₃ ·2H ₂ O	10.2	1110s, sp	1630sh 3400br	715w, 816m, 1020w, 1285vs 1305sh, 1430s, 1485s, 1520m
5.	(EDA)AgNO ₃ ·H ₂ O	9.2	1078m, sp	1630sh 3350br	705w, 808m, 815m, 1032w 1285s, 1300m, 1434vs, 1450sh, 1484vs, 1510m
6.	(BDA)AgNO ₃ ·2H ₂ O	6.1	1077m sp	1625sh 3420br	705m, 810m, 1021m, 1284vs 1310sh, 1430s, 1480vs, 1530m.

w, weak; m, medium; s, strong; vs, very strong; sh, shoulder.

of BDA (Table 1) indicates the presence of an equilibrium between covalent non-electrolyte structure and ionic structure $[L_2(H_2O)_2Ag][Ag(NO_3)_2(H_2O)_2]$ in solution^{12,13}.

EXPERIMENTAL

The ligands were prepared by the method of Chatt and Hart¹⁴. The molar conductances of millimolar solutions in nitrobenzene were determined on Toshniwal Conductivity bridge Type CLOI/OI. The ir spectra was recorded on Perkin Elmer Infrared Spectrophotometer Model 521. Carbon, Hydrogen, Nitrogen and Phosphorus analyses were carried out by Australian Micro-Analytica Service, Melbourne. Metal was determined by titrating against standard solution of ammonium thiocyanate in presence of dilute nitric acid.

Preparation of Complexes :

1. *Diaguobis (ethylenebisdiphenylphosphine)silver(I)Diaguodinitratoargentate(I)* : Ethylenebisdiphenylphosphine (0.48 g.) in 30 ml of acetone was added dropwise to silver nitrate (0.17 g.) in 3 ml of aqueous acetone with continuous stirring. After the completion of addition in about 30 min., the white complex was filtered, washed several times with water, acetone and dried under vacuum. Yield, 0.35 g., m.p. 268°. Found : C, 51.65; H, 4.34; N, 2.84; P, 10.47; Ag, 18.68. C₂₆H₂₈O₅NP₂Ag requires C, 51.60; H, 4.60; N, 2.31; P, 10.26, Ag, 18.0%.

2. *Diaguobis(ethylenebisdiphenylarsine)silver(I)dinitratoargentate(I)* : The ligand (0.58 g.) in 30 ml of acetone was added dropwise to a stirred solution of silver nitrate (0.17 g.) in 3 ml of aqueous acetone. The white complex was filtered, washed with water, acetone and dried under vacuum. Yield, 0.38 g., m.p. 227°. Found : C, 46.27; H, 3.38; N, 2.21; Ag, 16.03. C₂₆H₂₆O₄NAs₂Ag requires C, 46.30; H, 3.95; N, 2.08; Ag, 16.03%.

3. *Diaquonitrato(butylenebisdiphenylarsine) silver(I)* : The ligand (0.55 g.) in 35 ml of acetone was added dropwise to the stirred solution of silver (I) nitrate (0.17 g.) in 3 ml. of aqueous acetone. The addition was completed in 20 min. The white complex was filtered, washed with water, acetone and dried under vacuum. Yield, 0.38 g. m.p. 254°. Found : C, 46.67; H, 4.34; N, 2.07; Ag, 15.31. $C_{28}H_{32}O_5NAs_2Ag$ requires C, 46.66; H, 4.44; N, 1.95; Ag, 15.0%.

One of us (R.S.S.) is grateful to the Council of Scientific and Industrial Research, New Delhi for the award of a fellowship.

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